

SYNOVIAL HAEMANGIOMA OF THE KNEE JOINT: AN UNDERDIAGNOSED CASE IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY

Henry Yurianto^{*1}, M. Ruksal Saleh^{*}, Yohannes Toban Layuk Allo^{**} and Padlan^{**}

^{*}Staff of Orthopedic and Traumatology, Department Hasanuddin University Makassar., ^{**}Resident of Orthopaedic and Traumatology, Department Hasanuddin University Makassar.

ABSTRACT Introduction: Synovial haemangioma is a rare type of tumour with fewer than 200 cases have been published in the literatures worldwide. We present our experience with a synovial haemangioma of left knee joint that was preoperatively diagnosed as joint infection until the lesion was seen intraoperatively.

Case Report: An Indonesian male, 26 years old, came with chief complaint of continuous pain and swelling at left knee for around 8 months, with history of fever. There was history of prior debridement of knee joint with no relieved of symptoms. Physical examination revealed a scar at midline anterior, swollen and warm knee, and limited knee motion. The knee xray showed narrowing of joint space and lytic lesions at distal femur and proximal tibia.

Surgery revelealed an intraarticular red mass with villonodular nodules appearance measuring 2 x 1 and 1 x 1 cm. The mass was excised along with synovectomy. Histopathology showed soft tissue with proliferation of blood vessels of variable wall thickness characterized of synovial hemangioma. **Conclusion:** Delays in the diagnosis and treatment of synovial haemangioma can lead to long-term consequences including cartilage erosion and degenerative joint disease. Early recognition and complete excision can help avoid potentially irreversible joint damage.

KEYWORDS synovial haemangioma, knee joint

Introduction

Synovial haemangioma is a rare type of tumour which was first described by Bouchut in 1856. Fewer than 200 cases have been published in the literature worldwide. Synovial hemangioma occurs most frequently in the knee joint but is also found in other joints Since these lesions are uncommon and radiological findings are nonspecific, physician awareness is low, causing this lesion to be frequently misdiagnosed, leading in turn to treatment delays and irreversible complications of the affected joint. We here present our experience with a synovial haemangioma of the left knee joint that was preoperatively diagnosed

as joint infection until the lesion was seen intraoperatively, and diagnosed [1,2].

Figure 1:

Case report

An Indonesian male, 26 years old, admitted to the hospital in May 2016 with continuous pain and swelling at left knee, suffered since July 2015. The patient had a history of fever. There was a history of prior treatment by a general surgeon in October 2015 in which the patient received antibiotics injection and performed a debridement of the knee joint, without any information regarding the intraoperative results. The patient had no

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¹Staff of Orthopedic and Traumatology, Department Hasanuddin University Makassar;
Email: yohannestoban@gmail.com

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

relieved of symptoms and was referred to our hospital. Upon arrival, the patient was alert, well-nourished, and with normal vital signs. The local examination at his left knee showed a scar at the anterior midline aspect as long as 13 cm, with swelling and no change in skin colour (Figure 1,2,3). Upon palpation, there was tenderness and warmer knee than the surrounding area. There was no lymph nodes enlargement. There was a limitation of active and passive motion of the knee joint due to pain. The knee x-ray showed narrowing of joint space and lytic lesions at distal femur and proximal tibia (Figure 4). Laboratory examination showed leukocytosis and increased ESR. Diagnosis of the infected knee joint was made, and open debridement was planned for the patient. Surgery revealed an intraarticular red mass with villonodular nodules appearance measuring 2 x 1 and 1 x 1 cm (Figure 5,6). The mass was excised along with synovectomy. Histopathology showed soft tissue with the proliferation of blood vessels of variable wall thickness characterised by synovial hemangioma (Figure 7). At ten months follow up after the operation, the patient has a full range of motion of his left knee with mild pain during daily activity.

Discussion

Synovial haemangioma is a rare vascular malformation arising from the synovium-lined surface that usually affects children and young adults. They are typically diagnosed during the first to third decade of life. The most typical form of synovial hemangioma is the intraarticular type in which the tumour forms a mass lined by synovial membrane. Sixty percent of cases arise in the knee joint. Most of the synovial hemangioma involve the anterior compartment of the knee, either anterolateral or antero-medial region. Only 7% of cases of synovial hemangiomas of the knee arising from the infrapatellar region in reported cases. Synovial hemangiomas have also been found in the elbow, wrist, ankle and tendon sheath. There is a slight predilection of female to male patients [3,4].

The symptoms of synovial hemangioma occurring in the knee are non-specific. Patients can complain of pain, recurrent knee swelling, limitation of motion, painless mass, and recurrent intra-articular haemorrhage. Muscle atrophy may also be present and 40% of cases, with concomitant cutaneous haemangiomas. Because of the high incidence of synovial hemangiomas in adolescents or young adults, such patients might be notable for clinicians to evaluate the physical signs and clinical features accurately. Synovial hemangiomas of the knee are rare; very few

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

Figure 7:

clinicians have experience of the entity. Therefore, an accurate diagnosis before the operation is difficult. Thus, an accurate diagnosis before the operation is complicated. In the case of recurrent hemarthrosis, synovial hemangioma should be considered as a differential diagnosis in the absence of a coagulopathy. However, the majority of patients with synovial hemangioma presented with non-specific symptoms and signs, diagnosis is frequently delayed for several years. Delays in the diagnosis and treatment of synovial haemangioma can lead to long-term consequences including cartilage erosion and degenerative joint disease. Progressive joint destruction is believed to occur from intermittent bleeding into the joint resulting in inflammation and direct chondrotoxicity [4–6].

Plain radiography may be unremarkable in over half the patients. Phleboliths, soft tissue, periosteal thickening, advanced maturation of the epiphysis, and arthritic changes are occasionally present. While phleboliths may be present in all kinds of haemangioma occurring in any organ, they have visualised in only 50% of cavernous haemangioma and 30% of soft tissue haemangioma [1]. CT scan aids in demonstrating an intraarticular soft tissue mass but is non-specific for the diagnosis and demarcation of the tumour is usually not clear. Soft tissue hemangiomas have a special serpentine structure on contrast-enhanced CT images and T2-weighted MR images. Synovial hemangiomas, similar to soft tissue hemangiomas, also have serpentine vascular structures best seen on T2-weighted MR images. MRI findings of synovial hemangiomas are frequently pathognomonic: serpentine intraarticular mass with specified signal intensity. The mass usually intermediate signal intensity on T1-weighted images, and is marked hyperintensity on T2-weighted images reflecting pooling of blood in dilated vascular spaces. Low-signal-intensity linear structures on T2-weighted images are believed to represent fibrous septa or vascular channels [1].

Arthrography and arteriography are nonspecific. In the series by Devaney, three patients underwent arthrograms, none of which revealed a distinct intra-articular lesion. Synovial haemangioma is not sharply marginated and has no capsule, even though they are benign in nature. Their shapes usually follow the anatomic structure in which they are located [5].

According to the anatomic location, a synovial hemangioma can be divided into intraarticular, which is situated inside the joint capsule; juxta-articular, which is situated outside the joint

capsule; and intermediate, which are intra-articular as well as extra-articular location. In 1939, Benett divided synovial hemangiomas into diffuse and circumscribed types: the diffuse type usually consisted of a cavernous hemangioma with typical intermittent pain and swelling of the joint; circumscribed hemangiomas were a pedunculated synovial tumour of the capillary type. Histologically, Stout classified synovial hemangiomas into four main categories: cavernous, capillary, mixed cavernous capillary and venous. Synovial hemangioma with simple capillary wall and different degree dilated capillary spaces was classified as cavernous, mixed and capillary hemangioma, respectively. If the vessels have thickening walls and contain smooth muscle cells, the tumour is called venous hemangioma [3,5,7].

Histologic diagnosis is obtained by biopsy either arthroscopically or through open surgery. There is no consensus on the best treatment, but localised and small lesions may be excised arthroscopically whereas diffuse lesions are best addressed with open resection. Pre-operative embolisation may be useful to reduce bleeding. Careful and complete excision must be performed to prevent recurrence, and although there are no reports of recurrence in the literature, one patient in the series reported by Devaney et al. underwent a second surgery due to initial subtotal resection. Open synovectomy is preferred to arthroscopic synovectomy because the former allows broad exposure and therefore a better chance at complete excision, aside from the concern that intraoperative bleeding can make arthroscopic excision difficult [5,6].

Conclusion

Synovial hemangioma should be included as a differential diagnosis of knee pain, swelling, mass or recurrent hemarthrosis in adolescents or young adults without a history of trauma or coagulopathy. It has specific imaging characteristics with calcification or phlebolith on plain radiography and high signal serpentine vascular structures on T2-weighted MR images. Complete imaging should be sought in doubtful lesions. We advocate open arthrotomy and excision. Early recognition and complete excision can help avoid potentially irreversible joint damage.

Competing Interests

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